

THE ISSUE OF GENDER EQUALITY IN RAISING THE MORAL FACTORS OF SOCIETY

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Annotation. Our country is carrying out comprehensive reforms aimed at renewing the life of society, raising its spiritual sphere, modernizing it on the basis of modern science and national spiritual values. In this process, women are considered to be decisive force in ensuring the effectiveness of the spiritual factors of society. The article covers this issue in detail.

Keywords: spirituality, spiritual factors, civil society, globalization, spiritual immunity, "mass culture", gender equality.

Introduction. If we look at the history of the world, every nation has risen first of all with its spiritual unity and its national idea. Today, the issue of national ideology is very important in our country, which is on the path to building a new life and joining the ranks of developed countries. During the years of independence, great attention has been paid to strengthening the political foundations of the dynamics of change in the spiritual life of our society. During this period, a new type of Uzbek national statehood was established, this created wide opportunities for a new stage of development today [1].

Literature review. In recent years, a number of new reforms have been implemented to improve the spiritual life of the Society. The chairman of the Republican Council for Spirituality and Enlightenment is the President. The governors are responsible for the territorial divisions of the Council. This change has raised the spiritual and enlightenment work to a higher level in the policy of our state. It should be noted that the issues raised at the video conference chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on January 19 this year on radical improvement of the system of spiritual and educational work, strengthening cooperation between state and public organizations have opened a new era in this area. At this meeting, the head of our state noted that "If the body of society is the economy, its soul and spirit is spirituality" [2].

Maternal and methods. As we decide to build a new Uzbekistan, we will rely on two solid pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is the rich heritage of our ancestors and a strong spirituality based on national values. It is known that today in the world there is a fierce struggle and competition, the conflict of interests is growing. The processes of globalization are bringing unprecedented challenges along with incomparable new opportunities for humanity. Threats and dangers to national identity and spiritual values are increasing. Only self-centeredness, a light attitude to work, family, consumerism are masterfully absorbed into the minds of people, especially young people, in various ways. Threats such as terrorism, extremism, transnational and cybercrime, human trafficking, and drug trafficking are increasing. In some areas, there is deliberate instability and protests. In such a dangerous situation, it is more important than ever to increase the sensitivity of spiritual factors, to equip the minds of citizens with spiritual immunity on the basis of the idea of enlightenment against ignorance. First of all, it should be imply that women also have a special role in increasing the effectiveness of spiritual factors. They are primarily responsible for educating a healthy generation as educators of the nation. A woman is a person who forms the socio-moral qualities, spirituality in family members, first of all in her children. This function, which at first glance seems natural, requires from the woman herself socio-moral qualities and high spirituality. In order to fully fulfill the task of educating a harmoniously developed generation, it is necessary for women to be active in society, to have sufficient

knowledge, skills and abilities, to grow spiritually. Only in this way the spiritual-cultural and socio-moral upbringing processes in the family will active, continuous, in accordance with certain goals.

Results and discussion. In the process of building a new Uzbekistan, new political relations, worldviews and political culture are being formed. In this process, the interests of women must be reflected on a new scale and content, fully implemented, have a regular place in the public consciousness and should not lose their identity in any circumstances.

In the era of democratization of society, the attitude to women and the use of their life experience, intellectual potential and opportunities for the development of the society under construction serves to further increase the effectiveness of the spiritual factors of this society.

This means that an entire society should benefit from women's activism. It is becoming a topical issue of our time to reflect this activity and awareness in all spheres, that is, to ensure that our women are consciously involved in the ongoing reforms in the country. Because women have the power to positively address the most pressing and important issues for society, such as educating citizens, which is the foundation of civil society, democratic and tolerant thinking, commitment to progress and development. At the 75th session of the United Nations General Assembly, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said, "As a result of our large-scale measures for political, social and economic modernization of society, a new Uzbekistan is being formed. Today, democratic changes in our country have become irreversible.

For us, gender equality policy has become a priority. The role of women in public administration is growing. The number of women deputies in our new parliament has doubled."^[3]

Ensuring the employment of women, expanding opportunities for them to fully realize their aspirations and abilities is in the constant focus of our state. In particular, in order to increase the participation of women in public administration, a reserve of more than 6,000 active women has been formed. At present, systematic trainings are being organized to prepare them for various leadership positions.

In the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, 16 women held leadership positions, 6 women held governor positions, and 1 woman held embassy positions. In addition, about 1,500 women hold leadership positions at various levels.

According to the results of elections to the Oliy Majlis and local councils in December 2019, the number of women deputies accounted for 32% of the total number of deputies in the Legislative Chamber, women senators for 25% of Senate members and women for 25.6% in local councils. According to this indicator, the parliament of Uzbekistan ranks 44th among 190 parliaments in the world.

Conclusion. While the development and well-being of a society begins with ensuring the well-being of families, which is the smallest part, the formation of spiritual-cultural and socio-moral values in the family, increasing the sensitivity of spiritual factors does not occur separately from the social environment. In the process of radical changes in all spheres of society, along with the powers and responsibilities of citizens' self-government bodies, their responsibilities are also increasing. In the full implementation of these functions, it is possible to observe the activity of women in overcoming the shortcomings and problems in the system. By the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 200 of March 14, 2018, the position of a separate Deputy Chairman for Women's Affairs was introduced in each mahalla. Today, about 15,000 women work in this position throughout the country, protecting the rights and legitimate

interests of women, timely identification of their problems, socio-legal, psychological and financial assistance to women in need and in difficult social situations; ensuring women's employment, improving working conditions, attracting them to family and private entrepreneurship, crafts; with government agencies, non-governmental organizations and other civil society institutions in the implementation of measures for the early prevention of delinquency among women, individual work with those prone to delinquency, social rehabilitation and adaptation of women released from penitentiary institutions close cooperation; improving the reproductive health and medical culture of families; has been carrying out a number of tasks, such as strengthening family values and taking effective measures to prevent early marriages and divorces. It should be noted that despite the systematic work in this direction, there are a number of problems. It is known that on September 2, 2019, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On protection of women from oppression and violence" was adopted. The law establishes the practice of issuing "protection orders" to women who have been subjected to various forms of harassment and violence.

According to the Commission on Gender Equality of the Republic of Uzbekistan, so far, the police have received more than 7,000 applications for protection orders, and in 6,183 cases, protection orders have been issued to women. These figures show that the protection of the rights and interests of women, the further expansion of the scope of work on their full support should always be in the center of attention.

In a way of conclusion we can say that, first of all, "woman" and "family" are integral concepts. It is in the family and under the leadership of women that socio-moral values and spiritual factors are formed. Increasing the sensitivity of spiritual factors in society also begins with the family, which is its main link. Therefore, it is necessary to radically improve the preparation of women for marriage, with a special emphasis on women's education in the system of family-neighborhood-educational institution.

Second, the issue of women's employment is also important. It is necessary to increase the economic, socio-political and spiritual-cultural activity of women, to support women's entrepreneurship, to expand the activities of NGOs dealing with women's issues.

Third, it is worthwhile to widely cover and promote the role of women in ensuring the effectiveness of the spiritual factors of a renewed society in the media and on the Internet.

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